

Effect of Liquid Fertilizer on the Vegetative Growth of Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) and Soybean (*Glycine max*).

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ABSTRACT

The use of liquid fertilizers in agriculture has gained attention due to their potential to enhance plant growth and productivity. The study investigates the effect of foliar spray of liquid fertilizer on the vegetative growth of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) and soybean (*Glycine max*). The experiment was conducted in a greenhouse at the Botanical Garden Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, using polythene bags. Liquid fertilizer (SuperAgro) was prepared at 3 ml/L⁻¹, 2 ml/L⁻¹ and 1 ml/L⁻¹ and sprayed using a hand atomizer at a water carrier volume of 400 mL⁻¹ 4 m² while distilled water served as a control, and arranged in a randomized complete block design RCBD with three replications. Data was subjected to ANOVA using SAS Software 9.0 version. Means were separated using DMRT at $P < 0.05$. Growth parameters such as plant height, leaf area, stem circumference, and chlorophyll pigments were recorded. The result indicated significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in all parameters evaluated in the study in a concentration-dependent pattern, and the sorghum crop was more sensitive to the foliar spray of the liquid fertilizer.

Keywords: Liquid fertilizer, Soybean, Sorghum, Chlorophyll

INTRODUCTION

Sorghum has been cultivated for food and feed in America, Asia, Australia, and Africa ranked among the five main cereal crops in the world (Mace *et al.*, 2009; Venkateswaran *et al.*, 2014). It is a multipurpose crop cultivated for grain, sweet stem, forage, and broomcorn. It is a crop of great importance because of its ability to grow in tropical and subtropical semi-arid regions where rainfall is deficient and high temperatures predominate.

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) is a major oilseed crop produced and consumed worldwide. It is the main source of edible vegetable oil and high-quality vegetable protein and provides a high-quality raw material for producing forage for livestock and aquatic animals (Kim *et al.*, 2021; Harada and Kaga, 2019). Soybean protein is one of the high-quality vegetable proteins that have important health benefits and rich in essential amino acids, vitamins, flavonoids, and its meal accounting for about 70% of the total protein in soybean seed (Krishnan *et al.*, 2000; He and Chen, 2013; Kudelka *et al.*, 2021).

Liquid fertilizer provides nutrients according to the needs of plants (Ginandjar *et al.*, 2019). Foliar application of liquid fertilizer is an environmentally friendly and effective fertilization method with great potential to alleviate the soil and water pollution problems associated with excessive soil application of fertilizers. Liquid fertilizers offer advantages in terms of efficient nutrient delivery, reduced leaching potential, and precise application, which can help

mitigate the environmental impacts associated with granular fertilizers. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of liquid fertilizer on the vegetative growth of sorghum and soybean crops.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The experiment was carried out at the Ali Garko Botanic Garden, Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, Bayero University Kano.

Seed Collection

Sorghum seeds (SAMSORTG 45) and Soyabean (TGX-185-10E) varieties were obtained from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) and International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT), Kano.

Seed Planting and Fertilizer Application

Liquid fertilizer (SuperAgro-GNLD) was prepared at 3.0 ml/L (T1), 2.0 ml/L (T2), and 1.0 ml/L (T3) while distilled water served as a control (T4) and spray using a hand atomizer at a water carrier volume of 400 mL⁻¹ 4 m². Spraying was repeated twice at **7-day** intervals. Distilled water was sprayed on the control.

Data Collection

Data was collected on plant height, number of leaves, stem circumference, leaf area, and chlorophyll content.

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Plant Height

Plant height was measured from the base to the top of the main stem using a meter tape at 2-week intervals after seed germination, and the data were recorded in centimeters (cm).

Number of Leaves

The number of leaves was counted at 2-week intervals after germination, and the average was recorded.

Stem Circumference

A rope was used to measure the circumference, and the corresponding length was taken with the help of a ruler.

Leaf Area

Leaf area index is a dimensionless quantity that characterizes plant canopies. It was measured using the Leaf Area Meter LLAM-A10.

Chlorophyll Content

The Chlorophyll content was measured using a chlorophyll meter (CCM-200plus, Opti Sciences USA) model.

Statistical Analysis

The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) and four replications. Data was analyzed with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $p < 0.05$ using SAS software (9.0). Duncan Multiple Range Test at 5% degree of freedom.

RESULTS**Plant Height**

The result of the effect of foliar spray of liquid fertilizer on the plant height of the sorghum and soybean showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in seedling growth across the weeks in a concentration-dependent pattern (Table 1).

Table 1: Effect of liquid fertilizer on plant height (cm) of the sorghum and soybean

Treatments	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks
T1	48.07 ^a	63.71 ^a	68.42 ^a
T2	38.82 ^b	50.71 ^b	57.04 ^b
T3	29.70 ^a	30.67 ^a	36.78 ^a
T4	28.07 ^c	29.98 ^d	33.58 ^d
Variety			
SAMSORGT (45)	37.29 ^a	42.54 ^b	48.02 ^{ab}
TGX 1835-10E	34.77 ^a	50.13 ^a	53.34 ^a
LSD _{0.05}	5.92	6.84	11.84

Values with similar alphabet within the column are not significant at $p < 0.05$

Number of leaves

The result of the effect of liquid fertilizer on the number of leaves on sorghum and soybean showed

significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between treatments, with T1 and T3 scoring higher numbers of leaves (5.9) at 4 and 6 weeks (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of liquid fertilizer on the number of leaves on sorghum and soybean

Treatments	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks
T1	4.843 ^a	5.537 ^a	5.947 ^a
T2	4.167 ^{bc}	5.083 ^a	5.417 ^b
T3	2.450 ^a	5.333 ^a	5.917 ^a
T4	2.500 ^c	4.167 ^b	4.833 ^c
Variety			
SAMSORGT (45)	3.125 ^c	4.189 ^c	5.312 ^b
TGX 1835-10E	3.750 ^b	4.812 ^b	4.938 ^c
LSD _{0.05}	0.3585	0.3105	0.6210

Values with similar alphabet within the column are not significant at $p < 0.05$

Stem Circumference

The stem circumference of the sorghum and soybean showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in both

sorghum and soybean, while T1 and T2 expressed a close stem range at 6 WAS.

Table 3: Effect of liquid fertilizer on stem circumference (mm) of the sorghum and soybean

Treatments	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks
T1	2.687 ^a	3.423 ^a	4.463 ^a
T2	2.563 ^a	3.667 ^a	4.347 ^a
T3	2.517 ^a	3.163 ^a	3.780 ^b
T4	1.887 ^b	2.020 ^b	2.610 ^c
Variety			
SAMSORGT (45)	33.19 ^a	40.28 ^b	50.73 ^a
TGX 1835-10E	32.95 ^a	39.88 ^b	44.65 ^{ab}
LSD _{0.05}	0.3585	0.3105	0.6210

Values with similar alphabet within the column are not significant at $p < 0.05$

Leaf Area

Leaf area was significantly higher at T1 across the weeks. The results of liquid fertilizer on the leaf area of the sorghum and soybean indicated that there is a

significant difference between the leaf area in both sorghum and soybean at 2, 4 and 6 WAS after foliar spray of liquid fertilizer (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of liquid fertilizer on the leaf area of the sorghum and soybean

Treatments	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks
T1	47.87 ^a	64.87 ^a	78.97 ^a
T2	36.66 ^b	43.33 ^b	51.98 ^b
T3	28.35 ^c	34.62 ^c	37.91 ^c
T4	23.11 ^d	25.72 ^d	28.24 ^d
Variety			
SAMSORGT (45)	34.49 ^a	42.58 ^b	54.73 ^a
TGX 1835-10E	31.95 ^a	39.78 ^b	44.95 ^{ab}
LSD _{0.05}	0.3585	0.3105	0.6210

Values with similar alphabet within the column are not significant at $p < 0.05$

Chlorophyll Content

The result of the effect of foliar spray of liquid fertilizer on the chlorophyll content of the sorghum

and soybean and between treatments across weeks indicated no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) except at 6 WAS (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of liquid fertilizer on the chlorophyll content of the sorghum and soybean

Treatments	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks
T1	26.70 ^a	30.54 ^a	36.79 ^a
T2	27.73 ^a	30.03 ^a	36.68 ^a
T3	24.25 ^a	30.40 ^a	36.57 ^a
T4	26.70 ^a	30.98 ^a	36.12 ^b
Variety			
SAMSORGT (45)	25.74 ^a	35.99 ^a	40.37 ^a
TGX 1835-10E	22.65 ^a	29.78 ^a	34.48 ^a
LSD _{0.05}	0.3585	0.3105	0.6210

Values with similar alphabet within the column are not significant at $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

Foliar application of liquid fertilizers is a new strategy in modern crop management that increases nutrient use efficiency by direct nutrient absorption through the plant foliage. The foliar spray of liquid fertilizer showed a significant increase in plant height and number of leaves in both sorghum and soybean across the weeks. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have demonstrated the positive impact of fertilizer treatments on plant growth (Doifode, 2021; Noli and Aliyyanti, 2021). Liquid fertilizer treatments significantly increased stem circumference in both sorghum and soybean

plants compared to the control group at days 2, 4, and 6 weeks (Table 3). Gutiérrez-Miceli *et al.* (2008) reported an increased stem girth in *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench treated with the formulation of a liquid fertilizer. The study indicated that the foliar spray of liquid fertilizer significantly influenced leaf area in both sorghum and soybean plants across 2, 4, and 6 WAS. Plants treated with T1 (3 ml) of liquid fertilizer exhibited the largest leaf areas compared with the other concentrations and the control group, and likely provide optimal nutrient availability, supporting robust growth and physiological

performance in both crop species. The increased leaf area reflects enhanced photosynthetic capacity and overall plant vigour, and indicative of improved nutrient availability and uptake. Similar outcomes have been reported by Rizwan *et al.* (2021). Chlorophyll content remained consistent across all treatments and varieties, indicating that liquid fertilizer did not significantly affect chlorophyll production during the study period (Table 5). This result is in agreement with the findings of Qian *et al.* (2019). Foliar application is an environmentally friendly and effective fertilization method that has a great potential to alleviate the soil and water pollution associated with incessant application of granular fertilizer.

CONCLUSION

Investigation into the effect of liquid fertilizer on sorghum and soybean growth parameters revealed significant enhancements in plant height, stem circumference, and leaf area with the application of liquid fertilizer treatments. Additionally, the higher concentrations (3 ml/L) of liquid fertilizer exhibited greater vegetative advantage, highlighting the potential of liquid fertilizer in promoting structural and photosynthetic pigmentation for crop growth and development. The SAMSORGT (45) consistently demonstrated superior performance across multiple parameters. The robust growth and vigour displayed by SAMSORGT (45) underscore the suitability of foliar liquid fertilizer spray.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results obtained from this study, the recommended concentration of liquid fertilizer to farmers cultivating sorghum or soybean should consider foliar spray of SuperAgro liquid fertilizer at the best treatment (3 ml/L) for seedling vigour.

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